

Impact of information transfer on farmers' uptake of innovative technology

The Challenge

Current Scottish agricultural policy underlines the importance of widespread adoption by farmers of innovative technologies and practices to further improve the industry's performance, in which a significant role is played by the active exchange of technological knowledge between research and farming communities. This study analyses the impact of the transfer of technological information (among other a priori identified factors) on the adoption of innovative crop technologies by Scottish farmers.

Policy Implication

The findings indicate the factors which may influence the transfer of specific technological information targeted to the most likely technology adopters amongst agricultural producers. As education and information access were found to be among the factors influencing multiple technology adoption, attention should be paid to the provision of education and training on implementation of joint technologies and their collective impact on farm. The creation of centres of excellence that focus on particular aspects of farming, provision of professional development courses, and creation of demonstration farm networks could strengthen the links between research, education, extension and farmers, leading to the co-creation of knowledge better adapted to the needs of farmers. Farmers' adoption of interrelated agricultural innovations suggests the need for careful coordination between policies encouraging the adoption of some innovations with those promoting others.

Research

We used survey data of Scottish crop farms and structural equation modelling to test a conceptual model. This was based on behavioural economics theory and assessed the strength of the effects the behavioural determinants have on technology adoption intentions and behaviour.

Results

The results suggest that the key characteristics for identifying likely adopters of crop technologies such as precision farming, new tillage practices, novel crops, GM crops, biological control methods, and nitrogen fixing plants and/or legumes are: higher education level, active information seeking behaviour, profit orientation, higher agricultural income and proportion of the Single Farm Payment in total income, higher number of farm employees and positive investment behaviour. This confirms established evidence from the literature that, besides economic factors, access to technological information and trust in/perceived usefulness of the different information sources have an impact on technological uptake.

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Contact

Contact: Luiza Toma

Email: luiza.toma@sruc.ac.uk

Research group: Land Economy, Environment and Society

Address: SRUC, Peter Wilson Building, Edinburgh, EH9 3JG.

About

The Land Economy, Environment and Society (LEES) Research Group is one of the largest groupings of economists and social scientists working in the rural, agricultural and land based sectors in the UK. Our vision is to be recognised as one of the leading centres for agricultural and wider rural economic and social research globally, benefiting the land use sector, the environment and rural communities.

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